

Primer name	Sequence (5' to 3')	Target sequence
235	AACTGGGTGGTCTTGTTTGC	ssIGHV_L1_F
236	GGAGTAGAGCCCTGACGG	ssIGHG-R
246	GCCTCYTGCTGCTCTGG	IGKV1-F
247	TTCCCTGCTCAGCTCCTG	IGKV2-F
248	GACCACCCCATCCACTTTC	IGKC-R
251	CCTTGTCACCCTCCTCACTC	IGLV2-F
252	CTGGAYCCCTCTCCTGCTC	IGLV3-F
253	CCTGGACGGTGCTTCTGAT	IGLV8-F
300	GCGTCACTGTCTTCTCCACA	ssCL4_R

Table S3: Primers for amplification of porcine VH and VL genes.